

Prolonged Insurance in Disability Assessments with Eye Diseases in Veracruz South

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ABSTRACT

Temporary work disability is the loss of abilities that prevents a person from working for a certain period, protecting the worker's health and supporting their recovery. Objective: To analyze prolonged temporary disability in disability rulings due to ophthalmopathies in the Veracruz Sur region. Methods: A descriptive, retrospective, and cross-sectional study was conducted at the Regional Occupational Health Coordination, reviewing 176 rulings from July 2022 to July 2024. Diagnoses, duration of disability, and its prolongation were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. Results: The most frequent diagnosis was diabetic retinopathy with an average of 112.7 days of disability, followed by glaucoma with 252.6 days, and retinal detachment with 324.5 days. Conclusions: The disability durations for ophthalmopathies exceed the recommended maximums: 82 days for diabetic retinopathy, 45 days for glaucoma, and 82 days for retinal detachment.

KEYWORDS: Prolonged; insurance; eye; diseases; disability; determination.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Temporary disability benefits for work in Mexico, implemented by the Mexican Social Security Institute (Instituto Mexicano del Seguro Social, IMSS) more than 70 years ago, are intended to partially compensate for the income a worker loses when they are unable to perform their job duties due to illness or injury, within the framework of the general health insurance system (1). Temporary disability is defined as a health condition that prevents a worker from continuing their occupational activities, whether due to an acute or chronic illness or an injury (2)(3).

The assessment of this disability falls to the treating physician, who, based on the patient's clinical condition, determines the time required for recovery, aiming to prevent complications or relapses prior to the worker's return to work (4). Temporary disability benefits may be granted for up to 52 weeks, with a possible extension of 26 weeks in severe cases. However, when disability exceeds these time

limits, it affects both the worker and the institutions providing the benefit. Prolonged temporary disabilities negatively impact business productivity by reducing operational capacity and creating the need for staff replacement or task redistribution. In addition, they represent a significant economic burden on the social security system due to increased expenditures on medical services, prolonged treatments, and benefit payments (6)(7).

These types of disabilities also reflect broader occupational health issues, as they represent not only temporary illnesses but also cases that may progress to permanent disability. In such situations, greater medical resources are required, including specialized diagnostic procedures, prolonged treatments, rehabilitation, and follow-up, further increasing healthcare system costs (8). In order to optimize resources and improve the prescription of disability leave, medical committees and clinical guidelines have been developed to guide physicians on the appropriate duration of

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disability according to each pathology (⁹). Nevertheless, visual disorders remain a significant cause of disability, particularly diabetic retinopathy, a common complication of diabetes. Early detection is essential to prevent irreversible vision loss that may limit a worker's ability to perform occupational activities.

The analysis of prolonged temporary disabilities makes it possible to identify patterns and critical areas for the implementation of more effective strategies. This not only improves worker care and facilitates timely recovery but also helps preserve the sustainability of the social security system and reduces the economic impact on companies.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Following the evaluation and approval by the Local Research Committee and the registration in SIRELCIS under registration number R-2024-3101-070, a descriptive, retrospective, cross-sectional study was conducted using initial disability determinations due to ophthalmologic conditions, collected between July 2022 and July 2024 at the Delegational Coordination of Occupational Health of the OOAD Veracruz-Sur, in physical format.

An ad hoc data collection form was created to record variables such as sex, age, occupation at the time of the disability determination, and job seniority. Data were collected on the most frequent ophthalmologic conditions, the number of days of disability granted, and the duration of prolonged temporary disability.

The analysis was performed using SPSS version 24, applying mean, standard deviation, frequencies, and percentages.

III. RESULTS

All paragraphs must be indented. All paragraphs must be justified, i.e. both left-justified and right-justified A total of 176 disability determinations that met the inclusion criteria for this study were included and used for the analysis of results. Of the total sample of 176 disability determinations, 146 (83%) were men and 30 (17%) were women. The ages of workers with disability determinations due to ophthalmologic conditions ranged from 18 to 77 years, with a mean age of 59.6 years. The population was classified into five groups: Group A, patients aged 18–27 years, with a frequency of 3 (1.7%); Group B, aged 28–37 years, with 9 cases (5.1%); Group C, aged 38–47 years, with 41 cases (23.2%); Group D, aged 48–57 years, with 95 patients (54%); and Group E, aged 58–77 years, with 28 determinations (16%).

The job positions held at the time of the disability determination due to ophthalmologic conditions were grouped into categories based on the industry and activities performed at the time of assessment. Among the categories with the highest number of records were industrial machinery and transport operators, with 38 workers (21.5%), followed by agricultural workers with 26 cases

(14.7%), merchants and sales employees with 24 cases (13.6%), administrative workers with 21 cases (12%), and craft and construction workers with 18 cases (10.2%). Positions with fewer records included technicians and mechanics with 13 cases (7.3%), basic services and cleaning workers with 12 cases (7%), professionals with 10 cases (5.7%), security personnel with only 8 cases (4.5%), and 6 workers (3.5%) with non-specific activities classified as "other" (Figure 1).

For workers' job tenure, the length of service recorded in the disability determination was considered, corresponding to the time the patient had worked in their most recent job position. Thus, workers with a minimum tenure of 2 months and a maximum of 38 years were reported, with a mean of 13.38 years. This variable was described in six groups: Group A, 0–11 months, with 21 cases (12%); Group B, 1–5 years, with 52 cases (29.5%); Group C, 6–10 years, with 19 cases (10.8%); Group D, 11–15 years, with 19 cases (10.8%); Group E, 16–20 years, with 24 cases (13.6%); and Group F, those with more than 21 years of service, with 41 cases (23.3%).

Among the ophthalmologic conditions that resulted in a state of disability, diabetic retinopathy was the most frequent diagnosis, with a total of 129 cases (73%), followed by glaucoma with 11 cases (6.2%), retinal detachment with 6 cases (3.4%), blindness secondary to ocular globe trauma with 6 cases (3.4%), cataract with 4 cases (2.2%), macular degeneration with 4 cases (2.2%), corneal ulcer with 3 cases (1.7%), hypertensive retinopathy with 2 cases (1.1%), visual cortex disorders with 2 cases (1.1%), optic nerve disorders with 2 cases (1.1%), oculomotor nerve disorders with 2 cases (1.1%), and degenerative myopia with 2 cases (1.1%). Disability determinations with various other pathologies were grouped under the category "other", with 3 cases (Figure 2).

The month of onset of the condition recorded in the disability determinations was grouped into bimonthly periods: January/February, 48 cases (27.2%); March/April, 25 cases (14.2%); May/June, 26 cases (14.7%); July/August, 26 cases (14.7%); September/October, 18 cases (10.2%); and November/December, 33 cases (18.7%) (Figure 3).

The number of days of temporary work disability recorded overall prior to the state of disability was grouped as follows: 0–27 days, 35 cases (19.9%); 28–54 days, 18 cases (10.2%); 55–82 days, 22 cases (12.5%); 83–99 days, 12 cases (6.8%); and more than 100 days, 89 determinations (50.6%). According to measures of central tendency, a mean of 114.5 days was found, with a minimum of 0 days and a maximum of 382 days (Figure 4).

Those disability determinations that included more than 100 days of temporary work disability were classified as follows: 100–200 days, 52 cases (29.5%); 201–300 days, 33 cases (18.7%); and 301–400 days, 4 cases (2.2%) (Figure 5).

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The guideline for the duration of disability by pathology establishes recommended ranges of days according to the disease and workload, suggesting 27 to 82 days for diabetic retinopathy and retinal detachment, and 6 to 45 days for glaucoma. Regarding the number of days of temporary disability prior to the disability determination for the most frequent pathologies, it was found that for diabetic retinopathy the minimum number of days of disability granted was 0 days and the maximum was 232 days, with a mean of 112.7 days; for retinal detachment, the minimum number of days granted was 295 days and the maximum was 382 days, with a mean of 324.5 days; and for glaucoma, the minimum number of days granted was 233 days and the maximum was 288 days, with a mean of 252.6 days. According to the recommendations for retinal detachment, for which the maximum recommended duration is 82 days, 242 additional days beyond those required were granted (Figure 6).

IV. FIGURES

Figure 1. Job position held at the time of disability determination.

Workers whose job positions fell within the group of machinery operators and drivers represented the most relevant category, with 38 cases (21.5%), n = 176.

Figure 2. Ophthalmic conditions that resulted in a state of disability.

Retinopathy as a complication of diabetes mellitus was the most frequent cause of disability, accounting for 129 cases (73.3%), n = 176, among all ophthalmic pathologies.

Figure 3. Two-month period in which the onset of the condition was recorded.

A higher number of disability determinations were recorded with disease onset during the first two months of the year, 48 (27.2%), n = 176.

Figure 4. Days of temporary work disability recorded prior to the determination of disability status.

Eighty-nine assessments were found to report more than 100 days of temporary work disability (50.6%), n = 176.

Figure 5. Assessments with prolonged temporary work disability.

Those rulings that included 100–200 days of temporary work disability accounted for 52 cases (29.5%), n = 176.

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Figure 6. Average number of temporary work disability days recorded for diabetic retinopathy, glaucoma, and retinal detachment.

For diabetic retinopathy, a mean of 112.7 days was required; for glaucoma, 252.6 days; and for retinal detachment, 324.5 days.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Ophthalmologic conditions that lead to a state of disability are frequent, with diabetic retinopathy having the greatest impact due to the number of disability determinations generated annually. Among all the diagnoses identified, it is concluded that more than one hundred days of temporary work disability are frequently granted, far exceeding the number of days recommended in the “Guide for the Duration of Disability by Pathology in Support of the Prescription of Temporary Work Disability.” The prescription of disability leave is a task that is neither widely discussed nor fully understood in daily clinical practice, despite having significant repercussions on the dynamics of medical consultations, affecting workers, the Institute, and companies alike. This situation has a substantial impact on workers, the Mexican Social Security Institute (IMSS), and employers, as workers are not always able to return to their previous jobs due to the loss of essential visual capacities.

The need for appropriate and timely management of temporary disabilities is emphasized, requiring accurate diagnosis and a thorough understanding of current legislation, particularly in cases where clinical evolution is unlikely to improve, such as diabetic retinopathy, a disease with major public health impact and considerable economic and social consequences due to the prolonged duration of disability leave being granted and the poor occupational prognosis of affected individuals. Finally, the importance of a more structured and proactive approach is highlighted, supported by existing medical guidelines and protocols, to improve the prescription of temporary disability and ensure that patients receive appropriate care. Consultation with occupational medicine and the implementation of strategies for job reintegration or timely pensioning are essential to

prevent negative impacts on productivity and well-being for workers, companies, and social security institutions.

Limitations of this study include the absence of similar national studies and the fact that only one region was analyzed, which prevents determining whether this issue represents a national problem or is limited to the delegational level.

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